

ISic3598

I.Sicily inscription 3598

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stucco

Object

painted wall

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

necropolis on Capo Boeo

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491425

EDCS 46600167

Bibliography

1888-. *L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2007.0679

1923-. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 57.0880

Giglio, R. 2007. La cristianizzazione di Lilibeo attraverso le recenti scoperte archeologiche. In Bonacasa Carra, R.M., Vitale, E.(eds.), *La cristianizzazione in Italia fra tardoantico e altomedioevo*. Palermo. pp. 1779-1813. At 1785 B fig.9-11

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